

A Study of Some Controversial Issues in the Provisions of the Iddah in Islamic Jurisprudence and Personal Status Law in the Kingdom of Jordan

Author's Details:

¹ Nosaiba Younis Bsharat, ² Kamarudin Bin Awang Mat

nosaibabsharat61@gmail.com

^{1,2} Faculty of Contemporary Islamic Studies, University Sultan Zainal Abidin (UniSZA), Malaysia.

Abstract:

The problem is concentrated in the difference between the woman and her husband in the provisions of the iddah, as each interprets from his point of view, so there must be a clear reference that depends mainly on it. The study aims to clarify the provisions of the woman in the iddah in Islamic jurisprudence and the Jordanian personal status law, as well as a statement of what her financial rights are, and to identify the position of the Jordanian personal status law from the provisions of the iddah, in issues that agreed with Islamic jurisprudence, and issues in which jurisprudence was violated. Moreover, this study relied on the qualitative approach by extrapolating the scientific material from the books of jurisprudence from the four schools of jurisprudence, and the Jordanian Personal Status Law. Likewise, the comparative approach by comparing the legal schools with mentioning the sayings of the jurists, the position of the Jordanian Personal Status Law, and then analysing the articles of the law. The study concluded that the issues in which the Jordanian Personal Status Law violated Islamic jurisprudence were limited to the provisions of the Iddah, whether this Iddah was from divorce, or from death. Moreover, the Jordanian Personal Status Law has been silent about the inheritance of the divorced woman in a final divorce, and did not refer to her inheritance in a special text, and thus the Jordanian Personal Status Law violated Islamic jurisprudence, it is the duty of the Jordanian personal status law legislator to follow the Islamic jurisprudence approach in the issue of inheritance of the divorced woman through an irrevocable divorce, because the Jordanian personal status law is derived from Islamic jurisprudence, and in particular from the doctrine of Imam Abu Hanifa.

Keywords: controversial issues, iddah, Islamic jurisprudence, personal status law.

Introduction:

Praise be to Allah, we praise Him, we seek His forgiveness, we seek His help, we seek His guidance, and we seek refuge in God from the evils of ourselves and from the evils of our deeds. And I bear witness that there is no god but Allah, alone, without partner, and I bear witness that Muhammad is His servant and Messenger, He delivered the message, fulfilled the trust and advised the nation, so Allah rewarded him with the best of what He rewarded a prophet. Allah Almighty has honoured man. This honour came to distinguish man from the rest of the creatures, and Allah Almighty has legislated marriage between human beings as a manifestation of divine honour for them, because in this marriage there is peace, mercy and tranquillity. Preserving offspring, preserving humanity from extinction, and preserving life from diseases transmitted to humans if he establishes illegal relations outside of marital life.

But human nature requires that there be differences between husbands, and these differences lead to separation, whether divorce or annulment, and sometimes this separation occurs without a conflict between husbands, such as the death of the husband or wife, this separation entails special provisions relating to the husband or wife.

Islam has organized people's lives and their dealings and distinguished them over all other creatures, made marriage a Sunnah for them with its rulings, and made the jurists complete chapters detailed in its rulings and its consequences, and that one of its consequences in the organization may occur divorce is a legitimate solution to resolve disputes and search for a new beginning.

The Islamic Sharia also organized people's lives by making the consequences of divorce-related to the husband and wife, there is a need an iddah between the woman and man. The jurists have followed the provisions of the waiting period and separated them from its main sources, which are the Qur'an and the Sunnah, until the approach became clear to those who followed it.

This study came to show the provisions of the iddah in Islamic jurisprudence and the Jordanian Personal Status Law No. 36 of 2010, because of the very important doctrinal issues related to this topic, whether it is a revocable divorce period or an irrevocable divorce, or was it a iddah of deaths that entailed some provisions such as alimony, custody, breastfeeding, and inheritance.

Research problem:

The problem is concentrated in the difference that occurs between the woman in the iddah and her husband in the provisions of the iddah, as each is interpreted from his point of view and his knowledge, there must be a clear-cut reference that depends mainly on that, and several things are branched from this: Clarifying the difference that occurs between people in the provisions of the iddah, as each is interpreted from the point of view of his opinion and knowledge, it is necessary to have clear and well-defined references based on that. Also, an explanation of the differences of jurists in the provisions of the iddah, and this indicates the breadth of this religion and Allah's mercy on the worlds, as this indicates a vast jurisprudential wealth that the jurists collected from its fixed sources and derived it from their understanding of the Book of God and the texts of the purified Sunnah. And get acquainted with the position of the Jordanian Personal Status Law on the provisions of the iddah in issues in which Islamic jurisprudence agreed, and issues in which jurisprudence was violated, such as the departure of the iddah during the iddah. Whether it is several divorces, or several deaths, the reason for this is due to the reality of life in Jordanian society.

Research Importance:

The importance of this study appears in dealing with an important and basic matter of the reality of the life of the Islamic nation, which is the iddah. Especially for them, it is necessary to know these provisions clearly and in detail. It has several reasons, either it is caused by divorce, or the separation between husbands and their wives due to death, moreover, in both cases these divorced women or those whose husbands have died in the iddah entail special provisions for them, it is necessary to know these provisions clearly and in detail.

Literature Review:

- 1- Study: Muhammad (2015). entitled: "Iddah of death, its concept and provisions in Islamic law", an arbitrated research published in the Jerash Journal for Research and Studies, Jordan, No. 6, for the year 2015, which is a research in which it dealt with the legal rulings related to iddah of the woman whose husband died, Whether these rulings are devotional, financial, or social, whether they are pregnant or hindrance, whether they are entered into or not, divorced or not, Muslim or scriptural, and other separate rulings that most people are indispensable to know so that they do not fall into legal violations or confuse what is permissible or not permissible.
- 2- Study of Hanan (2012). Entitled: "The provisions of iddah in Islamic jurisprudence and the Syrian personal status law, iddah for death - iddah for divorce." Master's thesis, Damascus University, Syria, 2012 AD. It dealt with the definition of iddah, language and terminology, and then spoke about the two types of waiting in detail. And comprehensive, so I started with iddah of the woman whose husband had died, and detailed the provisions in them, by mentioning the provisions of the deceased, her husband and the pregnant woman, and then she mentioned the related provisions; Such as residence, alimony, mourning, and so on, then I spoke about iddah of the divorced woman, and detailed her ruling in the fact that the divorce occurred before consummation, or after it, and I spoke about the minor, and then followed that by mentioning the provisions related to this subject in an adequate and comprehensive manner.
- 3- Study: Abu Hussein (2010). Entitled: "Amended Articles in the Jordanian Personal Status Law No. (36) for 2010, Chapter on Divorce - Comparative Study -", which is a PhD thesis at the International University of Islamic Sciences, Amman, Jordan This study dealt with the case of the divorced man and the proof of his review of his divorced woman after the iddah and her marriage to another, as it dealt with the iddah in the correct contract and the corrupt contract, and the sayings of the jurists in

the right contract and the corrupt contract, as well as dealing with several menstruating women, and the divorced woman if she menstruates before Divorce, and the transition from a revocable divorce iddah to a death iddah, as well as a claim for alimony in iddah.

- 4- Study of Samira (2007). Entitled: "The provisions of iddah in Islamic jurisprudence - a comparative jurisprudence study-," Master's thesis, the Islamic University of Gaza, 2007 AD. It also dealt with separate provisions related to iddah, and the researcher compared between the provisions of iddah in Islamic jurisprudence and the Palestinian Personal Status Law.
- 5- Study of Muhammad (1977). Entitled: "Family Rulings in Islam" first edition, 1977 AD. In his book, he presented an introduction and three sections. He explained in the first section the marriage contract, its premises, its establishment, its pillars, its conditions, its place and its implications, and made the second section to discuss the termination of the contract. And an explanation of the types of separation, iddah, and others that result from the termination of married life. As for the third section, it was devoted to examining the rights of children such as lineage, custody, guardianship and alimony.

Research Methodology:

In this research, the researcher relied on both the qualitative approach by extrapolating the scientific material from the jurisprudence books of the four schools of jurisprudence, and the Jordanian Personal Status Law. It also relied on the comparative approach by comparing the jurisprudential schools with mentioning the sayings of the jurists, the position of the Jordanian Personal Status Law, and then analysing the articles of the law.

Conclusion

The law and jurisprudence agree in the provisions of the iddah of residence in the case of divorce, the law and jurisprudence are unanimously agreed on the obligation of residing in the iddah with a revocable divorce, as well as iddah pregnant widow with an irrevocable divorce. As for iddah who not a pregnant an irrevocable divorce, the residential law has given her in agreement with the opinion of the majority of jurists from the Hanafis, Malikis, Shafi'is and a group of Hanbalis.

We note also that the law obliges the iddah to divorce her for several maintenance, which includes housing, without looking at the type of divorce retroactively or irrevocably, and without looking at Al Baynunah: major or minor, We also note among the jurists, as it was looking at the pregnancy and the retention of the iddah without looking at the type of divorce or Al Baynunah.

Results:

- 1- That the law stipulated in the iddah that it had been entered into, it also stipulated that the home of the iddah, i.e., the residence of the deceased before his death, be owned by him the house, or a temporary benefit, and the benefit is absolute except for the temporary, or for a paid rent.
- 2- The woman in iddah of divorce during the illness of death, choose the longer of the two terms. This is because it is noticeable that the purpose of giving her the inheritance is to thwart the husband's bad behavior by divorcing her in a terminal illness, and to miss his intention for this, her iddah is the longer of the two terms.
- 3- There is no alimony for the deceased husband, whether she is pregnant or not pregnant, for the absence of the reason for the alimony, which is the contract according to the Hanafis, and the empowerment and enjoyment of the majority of the Malikis, Shafi'is and Hanbalis, when there was no reason for alimony, this was a reason for lack of alimony.

References:

- i. *Al-Hajjawi, M.A. Persuasion in the Jurisprudence of Imam Ahmad bin Hanbal, investigated by: Abdul Latif Muhammad Musa Al-Sabki, without its edition, Dar Al-Maarifa Beirut, without history.*

- ii. Al-Hattab A.S. (1992). *Talents of the Galilee in a Brief Explanation of Khalil*, 3rd Edition, Dar Al-Fikr, 1992 AD.
- iii. Al-Jarjani, A.M., (1983) *Book of Definitions, investigation: A group of scholars under the supervision of the publisher, i. 1*, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, Beirut, Lebanon, 1403 AH -1983 AD.
- iv. Al-Jassas, A.A, (1997). *Ahkam Al-Qur'an*, Dar Al-Fikr, 5/355, Al-Mardawi, Ala Al-Din Abu Al-Hassan Ali Bin Suleiman Ahmed, *Fairness in knowing the most correct of the dispute*, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, Beirut, i, 1997.
- v. Al-Jawhari, A.A, (1987). *Al-Sahih Taj Al-Lughah and Sahih Al-Arabiya, investigation: Ahmed Abdel-Ghafour Attar*, 4th edition, Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, Beirut, 1407 AH - 1987 AD.
- vi. Al-Jazaery, A. J. *Minhaj Al-Muslim*, 8th edition, Dar Al-Fikr Beirut.
- vii. Al-Jaziri, A.M.A., (2003). *Jurisprudence on the Four Schools*, 2nd Edition, Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya, Beirut, 2003 AD.
- viii. Al-Jundi, A.N, (2008). *Iddah of women After Separation or Divorce, I. 1*, Dar al-Kutub al-Qanuniyyah, 2008 AD.
- ix. Al-Kharshi, A.A. *footnote, on the summary of Sidi Khalil*, Dar Al-Fikr for printing, Beirut.
- x. Al-Takruri, O. *Explanation of the Jordanian Personal Status Law*, Dar Al-Thaqafa Library, Amman.
- xi. El-Gendy, A.N, *Divorce and Divorce and its Effect*, House of Legal Books, Egypt.